

The Development of OTOP Web Application: Case of Samut Songkhram Province

Authors : Satien Janpla, Kunyanuth Kularbphettong

Abstract : This paper aims to present the development of a web-based system to serve the need of selling OTOP products in Samut Songkhram, Thailand. This system was designed to promote and sell OTOP products on website. We describe the design approaches and functional components of this system. The system was developed by PHP and JavaScript and MySQL database System. To evaluate the system performance, questionnaires were used to measure user satisfaction with system usability by specialists and users. The results were satisfactory as followed: Means for specialists and users were 4.05 and 3.97, and standard deviation for specialists and users were 0.563 and 0.644 respectively. Further analysis showed that the quality of One Tambon One Product (OTOP) Website was also at a good level as well.

Keywords : web-based system, OTOP, product, website

Conference Title : ICEID 2014 : International Conference on Entrepreneurship, Innovation and Development

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : January 20-21, 2014